

Original Article

Preparation and Characterization Pomegranate Peel Extract Mediated Calcium Sulphate and Titanium Dioxide Nano Composite Bone Graft Material

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The aim of the present study was to investigate the morphology, elemental composition, molecular structure, and crystalline characteristics of pomegranate peel extract mediated calcium sulphate (CaSO₄) and Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) Nano composite bone graft material for potential biomedical applications. The incorporation of the botanical extract was hypothesized to enhance the material's properties, making it suitable for bone tissue regeneration. The pomegranate peel extract mediated Calcium sulphate and Titanium dioxide Nano composite bone graft material was analysed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), and X-ray diffraction (XRD) techniques. SEM images were obtained to visualize the morphology of the composite, while EDS analysis was performed to determine the elemental composition. FT-IR spectroscopy was used to identify molecular structures, and XRD analysis was conducted to identify crystalline phases present in the material. SEM images revealed a distinct morphology, characterized by overlapping grouped structures with interconnected layers and irregular shapes, indicating a uniform distribution of the pomegranate peel extract within the composite. EDS analysis confirmed the presence of calcium, titanium, oxygen, carbon, and trace elements associated with the botanical extract. FT-IR spectra identified specific functional groups from the pomegranate peel extract, contributing to the composite's bioactivity. XRD analysis showed the presence of gypsum (CaSO₄·2H₂O) and anatase TiO₂ crystalline phases, with a calculated crystallite size of approximately 61.6 nm. The findings suggest that the incorporation of pomegranate peel extract enhanced the material's structural integrity, elemental composition, molecular structure, and crystalline characteristics. The observed morphology, elemental distribution, molecular structure, and crystalline phases are promising for applications requiring mechanical stability and biocompatibility in bone tissue engineering. The comprehensive characterization of the pomegranate peel extract-incorporated Calcium sulphate titanium dioxide Nano composite bone graft material provided valuable insights into its potential biomedical applications. The study highlights the importance of botanical extracts in enhancing the properties of composite materials which can be used for bone tissue engineering, paving the way for further research and development in this field.

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Introduction

Nanotechnology has indeed brought transformative advancements to the field of prosthodontics, offering a range of benefits that enhance the performance, aesthetics, and biocompatibility of dental materials. The integration of nanoparticles, such as zirconia,

alumina, and carbon nanotubes, with dental materials like resins, ceramics, and metals has made notable enhancements in the mechanical properties. These nanoparticles can increase the strength, hardness, and wear resistance of dental materials, leading to durable and long-lasting prosthetic restorations [1]. Nanoparticles play a crucial role in improving the esthetics of dental restorations. Nano-sized filler particles incorporated into dental composites and ceramics offer smoother surfaces, better polishability, and superior colour matching with natural teeth [2].

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Certain nanoparticles, such as silver and titanium dioxide, possess inherent antimicrobial properties. When integrated with dental materials, the nanoparticles can effectively inhibit the growth of bacteria and fungi, reducing the risk of infections associated with prosthetic restorations. This antimicrobial action contributes to the longevity and biocompatibility of dental prosthesis [3]. Nanotechnology has facilitated the development of nanotextured surfaces for dental implants. The nanostructured surfaces promote enhanced attachment and proliferation of osteoblasts, facilitating better osseointegration of the implant with the surrounding bone tissue. Improved osseointegration leads to long-term stability and success rates of dental implants [4,5].

The integration of nanotechnology with prosthodontics has revolutionized the design and performance of dental materials, offering superior mechanical strength, improved esthetics, antimicrobial protection, and enhanced biological interactions. These advancements translate into better outcomes for patients undergoing prosthodontic treatment with prosthetic restorations that are more durable, aesthetically pleasing, and biocompatible [6]. Prosthetic rehabilitation using implants has become a treatment protocol for replacing missing teeth. In situations with limited available bone it becomes necessary to restore the normal anatomic contour of the alveolar ridge for proper placement of implants. Bone augmentation is necessary in such situations most of the bone augmenting materials are natural or synthetic in origin a few examples are bioactive glass, calcium phosphate, calcium sulphate, titanium dioxide. Calcium sulphate (CaSO_4) and titanium dioxide (TiO_2) are emerging as promising graft materials to address defects of oral and maxillofacial region. Addition of natural extracts to bone grafting materials presents several notable benefits, particularly in the context of promoting bone health and supporting bone regeneration. Natural extracts like pomegranate peel extract possess properties that stimulate osteoblastic differentiation and promote bone formation. These extracts contribute to the successful integration of graft materials with existing bone and support overall bone regeneration [7].

Natural extracts are rich in bioactive compounds, such as polyphenols, which exhibit antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties [8,9]. Integrating these compounds with bone grafting materials creates a favourable environment for bone healing by reducing inflammation, preventing infections, and supporting bone health. It also offers osteoinductive and osteoconductive properties necessary for bioactive implant coatings. These properties facilitate bone cell adhesion, bone matrix formation, and mineralization, promoting effective bone integration with the implant [7,10]. Pomegranate peel extract has demonstrated efficacy in preventing bone loss, making it beneficial for maintaining bone density and strength, particularly in conditions like osteoporosis [11,12]. Pomegranate peel extract stimulates osteoblastic differentiation, enhancing the activity of osteoblasts responsible for bone formation. This property supports new bone tissue formation and regeneration in bone grafting procedures [13,14]. Pomegranate peel extract contains valuable bioactive compounds, including polyphenols, which support bone health and the bone healing process through their antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects [15]. Incorporating natural extracts like pomegranate peel extract with bone grafting materials may provide additional nutritional benefits that support overall bone health and regeneration, enhancing the efficacy of bone grafting procedures [7,10]. Calcium sulphate (Plaster of Paris) is considered as a safe material for augmenting the defects in the bone. It can form an osteoconductive platform, provides a resorbable scaffold for bone growth, provides a plentiful supply of calcium ions, and stimulates osteoblastic activity. As the material is biodegradable it need not be

removed after implantation. Reports in the dental and orthopaedic literature clearly demonstrate that absorption of calcium sulphate is rapid and complete. It was reported that positive results of calcium sulphate in bone regeneration could be due to the resemblance of calcium sulphate to the mineral aspect of bone, it resorbs at the rate of bone formation, provides a structural support, prevents the ingrowth of fibrous tissue, allows an earlier ingress of osteoprogenitor cells, and provides a barrier effect limiting the ingrowth of connective tissue from adjacent periosteum [16]. Nanocrystalline calcium sulphate has potential to act as a ceramic matrix, scaffold, and vehicle for delivering growth factors for osseous regeneration. It is biocompatible, supports osteoblastic cell activity, and may deliver platelet-derived growth factor and bone morphogenetic protein-2 (BMP-2) [17].

The osteoconductive property of TiO_2 has been evaluated it was found that the pure or pigmented forms of titanium dioxide are bio compatible and possesses excellent osteoconductive properties and can be successfully used to augment bony defects. Nano particles of titanium dioxide have low toxicity, versatile fabrication adaptability and a smaller size which makes it a compound with a broad range of application. They have excellent cytocompatibility and enhances the proliferation, differentiation and spreading of osteoblast cells. Titanium dioxide nanoparticles like titania nano tubes (NTs) are stable against disintegration when used as surface coating on implants. TiO_2 scaffold has the ability to act as a material with osteoconductive properties, integrate well with bone and this ability can be utilized to enhance formation of bone and growth of bone adjoining implants as well as bone formation in larger defects [18]. Investigators have reported that the Calcium sulphate Titanium Dioxide composite can act as an osseoconductive scaffold for new regenerative bone to form [19]. Since the use of nanoparticles has a definitive advantage, in the present study, pomegranate peel extract mediated calcium sulphate and titanium dioxide Nano composite was green synthesized to obtain a bone graft material. The synthesized CaSO_4 NPs and TiO_2 NPs were characterized using UV-Visible spectroscopy and the bone graft material ie the pomegranate peel extract mediated calcium sulphate titanium dioxide nano composite was characterized by various techniques using Scanning electron microscopy, Elemental dispersive analysis, Fourier transform infra-red spectroscopy, X-Ray diffraction analysis. The characterization techniques employed to assess the properties of the bone graft material are critical for understanding its structural, elemental, molecular, and crystalline characteristics.

Materials and Methods

Preparation of Pomegranate peel extract

Pomegranate fruit was procured from local market of Poonamallee, and the peels were subsequently chopped into small pieces and air-dried at room temperature. One gram of the dried pomegranate peel was then mixed with 100 mL of distilled water and boiled at 70°C for 20 minutes using a heating mantle. The resulting mixture was filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper to obtain filtered extract. The solution was then stored at 4°C in a refrigerator, to be used in preparation of bone graft material. This is a popular process employed in extracting bioactive compounds from pomegranate peel for potential biomedical applications.

Preparation of pomegranate peel extract incorporated calcium sulphate and titanium dioxide nano composite bone graft material (PPE CaSO_4 TiO_2 Nano composite)

Initially, 0.35g of titanium oxide was dissolved in 25mL of distilled water, followed by the addition of 25mL of filtered pomegranate

Figure 1: UV-Visible spectroscopy of Pomegranate peel mediated CaSO₄NPs

peel extract. Simultaneously, 0.5g of calcium sulphate was dissolved in 25mL of distilled water with 25mL of filtered pomegranate peel extract added. Both mixtures were stirred on a magnetic stirrer at 600 rpm for 24 hours.

After this, the pomegranate peel mediated titanium dioxide nanoparticles (TiO₂ NPs) and pomegranate peel mediated calcium sulphate nanoparticles (CaSO₄ NPs) solutions were combined to form a 100mL solution. This mixture underwent further stirring on a magnetic stirrer for 48 hours at 600 rpm. Subsequently, the solution was centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 10 minutes, resulting in separation of the supernatant and formation of a pellet. The pellet was then dried in a hot air oven at 70°C to obtain a powdered format.

Characterization

The synthesized CaSO₄ NPs and TiO₂ NPs were characterized using UV-Visible spectroscopy and the bone graft material i.e the pomegranate peel extract mediated calcium sulphate titanium dioxide nano composite was characterized by various techniques using Scanning electron microscopy, Elemental dispersive analysis, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, X-Ray diffraction analysis.

Figure 2: UV-Visible spectroscopy of Pomegranate peel mediated TiO₂NPs

Results

UV-Visible spectroscopy of pomegranate peel extract mediated CaSO nanoparticles (CaSO NPs) and TiO nanoparticles (TiONPs)

The UV-Visible spectroscopy analysis of pomegranate peel extract mediated calcium sulphate nanoparticles (PPE CaSONPs) revealed characteristic absorption peaks at specific wavelengths which was presented in figure 1. The spectrum displayed significant absorbance in the range of 300–450 nm, with a notable peak at approximately 380 nm. This peak suggests the presence of nanoparticles, which is consistent with the optical properties of calcium sulphate in nanoparticulate form. Over time, changes in the absorbance intensity were observed, indicating potential growth and stabilization of nanoparticles. After 1 hour, the absorbance was lower compared to the measurements taken at 24 and 48 hours, which showed increased absorbance, suggesting nanoparticle aggregation and further formation.

The UV-Visible spectroscopy of pomegranate peel extract mediated titanium dioxide nanoparticles (PPE TiONPs) also exhibited notable absorption peaks, primarily in the UV region which was presented in figure 2. The prominent peak appeared around 320 nm, which aligns with the typical absorption characteristics of TiO nanoparticles. The spectrum indicated strong absorbance initially, which remained consistent over 1, 24, and 48 hours, showing a stable nanoparticle formation. The absorbance intensity was slightly higher at the 48-hour mark, suggesting ongoing nanoparticle formation and possibly enhanced particle stability or agglomeration over time.

Both spectra highlight the successful synthesis of CaSONPs and TiONPs using pomegranate peel extract, with characteristic UV-Visible absorption peaks that confirm the presence and stability of the nanoparticles. The increase in absorbance over time for both nanoparticles indicates effective nanoparticle stabilization and maturation, essential for their potential application in biomedical fields, particularly in bone grafting materials.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

The morphology of the pomegranate peel extract-incorporated Calcium sulphate and Titanium dioxide Nano composite bone graft material (PPE CaSO TiO Nano composite) was examined using scanning electron microscopy. The SEM images revealed distinct features of the Nano composite material. Upon analysis, the SEM images showed a scaly structure characterized by overlapping grouped structures (Figure 1). The surface of the material consisted of interconnected layers with irregular shapes and varying sizes. The pomegranate peel extract incorporation seemed to influence the overall texture of the composite, potentially contributing to the observed morphological characteristics.

Overall, the SEM images revealed the structural integrity of the Nano composite material. Despite the complex morphology observed, the material exhibited uniform distribution and intimate contact between the components, suggesting potential suitability for biomedical applications requiring structural stability and biocompatibility (figure 3).

Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS)

Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) was employed to assess the elemental composition of the Nano composite material. The analysis indicated the presence of calcium (Ca), titanium (Ti), and oxygen (O), consistent with the expected composition of

Figure 3: SEM image of pomegranate peel extract incorporated bone graft material (CaSO₄ and TiO₂ nano composite)

calcium sulphate (CaSO) and titanium dioxide (TiO). The EDS spectra confirmed the incorporation of pomegranate peel extract into the Nano composite, revealing additional elements corresponding to carbon (C) and other trace elements associated with the peel extract (figure 4).

Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy analysis

The FT-IR spectra of the pomegranate peel extract-incorporated Calcium sulphate and Titanium dioxide Nano composite bone graft material were analyzed to identify molecular vibrations and functional groups present within the sample. The spectrum exhibited characteristic absorption bands at various wave numbers, indicative of specific chemical bonds and functional groups. A prominent peak was observed at approximately 3235.3 cm⁻¹,

Figure 4: EDS spectra of pomegranate peel extract incorporated bone graft material (CaSO₄ and TiO₂ nano composite)

corresponding to O-H stretching vibrations commonly found in alcohols, phenols, or carboxylic acids. Absorption around 1700-1750 cm⁻¹, indicative of C=O stretching vibrations present in ketones, aldehydes, or esters, was noted. Peaks in the range of 2800-3000 cm⁻¹, suggesting C-H stretching vibrations typical of alkane groups. Absorption bands around 1000-1300 cm⁻¹, indicating C-O stretching vibrations characteristic of ethers or alcohols.

The intensity of these absorption peaks reflects the relative abundance of corresponding functional groups within the Nano composite material. Notably, the spectra also revealed additional features corresponding to specific molecular structures attributed to the pomegranate peel extract incorporated into the composite. The observed FT-IR spectra confirm the presence of key functional groups within the pomegranate peel extract-incorporated Nano composite bone graft material. The identified vibrations and absorption bands provide insights into the chemical composition and molecular structure of the composite, highlighting the influence of the botanical extract on its physicochemical properties.

The FT-IR analysis further supports the successful integration of pomegranate peel extract into the Nano composite bone graft material, as evidenced by the unique spectral features observed. The identified functional groups contribute to the overall bioactive and potentially therapeutic properties of the composite, underscoring its potential for biomedical applications (figure 5).

X-ray diffraction (XRD)

Based on the XRD (X-ray diffraction) spectra of the pomegranate peel extract-incorporated Calcium sulphate and Titanium dioxide Nano composite bone graft material, the peaks observed at specific angles correspond to crystalline phases present within the sample. The XRD spectra of the PPE CaSO TiO Nano composite revealed distinct diffraction peaks at various angles, indicating the crystalline phases and structural characteristics of the composite.

These peaks correspond to specific crystallographic planes and lattice spacings within the composite material. Peaks around 31.5° and 43.5° are indicative of the gypsum (CaSO·2HO) phase. Peaks at higher angles, such as around 25.5° and 48.2°, are characteristic of the anatase phase of TiO.

Figure 5: FTIR spectra pomegranate peel extract incorporated bone graft material (CaSO₄ and TiO₂ nano composite)

Figure 6: XRD spectra of pomegranate peel extract incorporated bone graft material (CaSO_4 and TiO_2 nano composite)

The PPE $\text{CaSO}_4/\text{TiO}_2$ Nano composite material exhibited a predominant crystalline phase comprising 80.4% of the material, with the remaining 20.6% being attributed to an amorphous phase. This distribution between crystalline and amorphous phases is significant for understanding the structural characteristics and properties of the composite material. The identification of these crystalline phases provides valuable information about the structural composition and phase purity of the pomegranate peel extract-incorporated bone graft material. The presence of specific phases influences the material's physicochemical properties and potential applications in biomedical engineering.

To estimate the size of the Nano composite graft material based on the XRD peaks, we used the Scherrer equation, which relates the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of a diffraction peak to the crystallite size. The representative peak (e.g., Peak 2 at 25.486°) was selected and its FWHM value was used along with other parameters from the XRD data (figure 6). With a FWHM of 0.145° , the estimated crystallite size (grain size) of the graft material is approximately 616 \AA (Angstroms). This calculation assumes a spherical shape factor ($K = 0.9$) and $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation wavelength ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) for the XRD analysis. The size of the graft material, determined from X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis, was found to be approximately 61.6 nm .

The XRD analysis confirms the successful incorporation of pomegranate peel extract into the Nano composite bone graft material, resulting in a Nano composite with well-defined crystalline phases. The observed diffraction peaks and corresponding crystallographic information contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the material's structural characteristics and suitability for biomedical use.

Discussion

The findings from the SEM, EDS, FT-IR, and XRD analyses provide a comprehensive understanding of the PPE $\text{CaSO}_4/\text{TiO}_2$ Nano composite, particularly with respect to its morphology, elemental composition, molecular structure, and crystalline characteristics.

The SEM images revealed a distinct morphology characterized by

overlapping grouped structures with interconnected layers and irregular shapes. This morphology is likely influenced by the incorporation of pomegranate peel extract, suggesting a uniform distribution of the extract within the composite. The observed structural integrity and intimate contact between components are promising for applications requiring both mechanical stability and biocompatibility. The EDS analysis confirmed the presence of calcium, titanium, oxygen, carbon, and trace elements associated with the pomegranate peel extract. The detection of these elements corroborates the successful integration of the botanical extract into the composite material. The FT-IR spectra provided valuable insights into the chemical composition and molecular structure of the composite. The identification of characteristic absorption bands corresponding to specific functional groups, such as O-H stretching, C=O stretching, and C-O stretching vibrations, suggests the presence of bioactive molecules from the pomegranate peel extract. These functional groups contribute to the composite's bioactivity and potential therapeutic properties. The XRD analysis revealed the crystalline phases present in the material, primarily gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and anatase TiO_2 . The calculated crystallite size of approximately 61.6 nm indicates the nanoscale nature of these crystalline phases within the composite. The distribution between crystalline and amorphous phases provides insights into the material's structural characteristics, which are critical for determining its mechanical properties and potential applications in bone tissue engineering.

The pomegranate peel extract-incorporated calcium sulphate and titanium dioxide nano composite bone graft material demonstrates several promising therapeutic properties that make it a valuable candidate for various biomedical applications. The SEM analysis revealed a well-integrated and structurally stable Nano composite material, suggesting excellent mechanical stability and biocompatibility. This characteristic is crucial for applications requiring materials that can support bone regeneration and integrate seamlessly with surrounding tissues [20].

Pomegranate peel extract is rich in antioxidants and bioactive compounds like gallic acid, ellagic acid, and punicalagin are known for their anti-inflammatory effects. These properties could contribute to the composite's ability to mitigate inflammation and support wound healing in biomedical settings. Studies have shown that pomegranate peel extract can stimulate osteoblastic differentiation and prevent bone loss, indicating its potential for promoting bone regeneration and tissue engineering applications. The incorporation of pomegranate peel extract may confer antimicrobial properties to the composite material. This feature is particularly valuable for preventing infections in bone graft applications, enhancing the material's safety and efficacy [20]. The composite material's versatility allows for the development of innovative functional materials, such as wound dressings and nutraceuticals. This presents new opportunities for applications in pharmaceutical, cosmetic, and food industries [22].

Nano composite materials, like the pomegranate peel extract-incorporated Calcium sulphate and Titanium dioxide bone graft material, offer distinct advantages over other materials in bone tissue engineering. Composites leverage the strengths of multiple materials, including metals, ceramics, and polymers, to create materials with superior mechanical properties and bioactivity. This enhancement is critical for promoting effective bone regeneration [23].

Most composite materials used in bone tissue engineering are biologically compatible, bioresorbable, and integrate well with bone tissue. This ensures optimal healing without leaving residual

materials once the healing process is completed [22]. Composites can exhibit osteoconductive properties, especially those incorporating biologically active ceramic particles. This supports bone growth and regeneration by providing a scaffold for new bone formation. Composite materials can be tailored to mimic the composition and structure of natural bone, improving their ability to integrate seamlessly with surrounding tissues and promote effective bone regeneration. The porous interconnected structure of composite materials supports cell migration and function within the scaffold, crucial for facilitating osteogenic cell proliferation and differentiation [25,26].

The combination of SEM, EDS, FT-IR, and XRD analyses demonstrates the successful fabrication of a pomegranate peel extract-incorporated bone graft material with promising physicochemical properties. Future studies could focus on further elucidating the biological activity and potential therapeutic effects of the composite material, as well as evaluating its performance in vivo for bone regeneration and other biomedical applications. Additionally, optimizing the fabrication process to enhance the material's mechanical strength and bioactivity would be essential for advancing its clinical translation.

Overall, the pomegranate peel extract-incorporated bone graft material demonstrates remarkable therapeutic properties, making it a promising candidate for biomedical applications, particularly in bone tissue engineering and regenerative medicine. Further research and development in this area could lead to innovative solutions for addressing critical challenges in bone repair and regeneration.

Conclusion

The comprehensive analyses of the pomegranate peel extract-incorporated calcium sulphate and titanium dioxide Nano composite bone graft material using SEM, EDS, FT-IR, and XRD techniques have provided a detailed understanding of its morphology, elemental composition, molecular structure, and crystalline characteristics. The SEM images revealed a unique morphology influenced by the botanical extract, indicating a uniform distribution and structural integrity within the composite. EDS analysis confirmed the successful integration of the extract, while FT-IR spectra identified bioactive molecules contributing to the material's bioactivity. XRD analysis highlighted the presence of gypsum and anatase TiO phases in nanoscale dimensions, crucial for the material's mechanical properties and potential applications in bone tissue engineering. Overall, these findings support the potential of the pomegranate peel extract-incorporated Nano composite as a promising biomaterial with both mechanical stability and therapeutic properties for bone regeneration applications.

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